

BASIC REQUIREMENTS FOR DIGITAL BANK: BANKING PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation: *This article discusses digital banking that meets current modern standards. The principles that a digital bank should set up are presented in sections. The role and importance of IT in the banking sector is widely covered. Research in this area has been studied and used as data.*

Keywords: *Financial services, Digital banking, IT, AI, business model.*

The system of modernization and simplification of banking services plays an important role in the development of financial services in the country. Today, information technology is widely introduced into the banking system, as in all areas. The development of digital banking in the banking system is one of the key issues of economic growth, especially during the global coronavirus pandemic.

Research shows that a bank or its subsidiary that provides remote banking services using innovative

banking technologies (without providing cash services) is a digital bank. This is the definition given to an entire bank or bank branch. Digital banking should be considered as a software package for online delivery of banking products to users of banking services. “Digital banking is a new form of interaction between a bank and its customers, including innovations in the field of financial services for consumers and commercial clients in the areas of digital, information and technology strategies,” A.A. Gontar said.

Researchers Suchat Tungjitnob, Kitsuchart Pasupa, Boontawee Suntisrivaraporn, in their research, expressed the following views on "Mobile banking": In addition, the mobile banking app will reduce the cost of adding additional branches. The bank will also benefit from getting customer information from the app. "

"Research in developed countries has shown that e-banking reduces operating costs and is therefore a major benefit for banks.

Banks are not alone in using older systems. For example, the U.S. Nuclear Forces still relies on a computer system from the 1970s and 8-inch floppy disks.

FIGURE 7.2 The investor's view of the DBF

Pay attention to the investor's lens in the digital bank, as shown in Figure 7.2. A digital bank is by its very nature a cross between a fintech company and a bank. Although digital banking, like traditional banking, can be divided into five divisions (retail banking, private and business banking, analysis and IT, finance and operations

management, and risk management), the relative importance of these divisions is one. not the same. In addition, the map of the relationship between the different divisions differs in digital and old banking, analysis and IT form the basis of the digital banking building. In general, the success or failure of a bank is measured by the

technologies and analytical methods used, for example:

New IT infrastructure. Building a digital bank from scratch allows you to create a flexible IT infrastructure that provides modern risk management, helps optimize the bank's balance sheet, and helps ensure that capital is significantly higher than those with income and ensures compliance. continuous change of banking rules in real time, which is achieved by creating opportunities for modern regulatory technologies.

Database design. The IT technology of a digital bank is based on modern database technology that can cope with exponential data growth, new internet technologies and analysis methods. This technology uses a distributed notebook system.

Advanced data analysis. As banks have abundant stocks of raw behavioral data that provide valuable information about customers' future choices, the value proposition offered by digital banking can be expanded. In the example of internet energy hubs such as Google, Amazon, Alibaba and Facebook, a bank needs to combine

data on deposits, consumer finance and other transaction accounts for a single view of customer activity. For example, customers' in-store payments are much more accurate than traditional profile data (e.g., age, income, geography) in predicting their future financial performance and creditworthiness. The geophysical mobility of customers between stores provides further improvements. In addition, using customer data, digital banks can create offers ranging from payment solutions and information services, from the right to accept savings and deposits, to online banking, consulting services and simple financing. It is very important to evaluate the accumulated transactions of customers in real time and connect them to study in depth and predict future customer behavior using other probability algorithms. It is very important to create a guarantee of personal inviolability in accordance with the wishes and legal requirements of customers.

AI. Autonomous selection of the best methodology when data is provided arbitrarily allows banks to

adapt to new data and dynamically shape their clients' full financial profile, including creditworthiness, borrowing ability, and risk appetite for financial planning. In addition, artificial intelligence can quickly adapt to customer needs and change dynamically with customer development, providing the best offer at the right time. A smart bank can take advantage of changes in a customer's life cycle faster and help the customer achieve their financial goals.

Full stack business model. A full stack business model is critical to the overall customer experience. This approach facilitates compliance by the bank with a regulatory framework that ensures the prevention of money laundering and fraud and guarantees customer protection. In general, intelligent fraud detection and correction systems can operate at a

much higher rate than traditional methods.

When done correctly, bulletproof security and customer protection offer digital banks a significant competitive advantage over other financial service providers. These features are included in the secure IT architecture from the outset and prevent data misuse and sale to third parties. Naturally, they involve the implementation of new cryptographically protected distributed data management.

Using a distributed ledger reduces financial transaction costs, improves the stability of the entire system, and reduces operational risks. Undoubtedly, the distributed ledger will be related to the operational procedures of the digital bank and its interactions with other digital, old and central banks.

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